

Optimal Placement of Processors based on Effective Communication Load

A. R. Aswatha, T. Basavaraju, and N. Bhaskara Rao

Abstract—This paper presents a new technique for the optimum placement of processors to minimize the total effective communication load under multi-processor communication dominated environment. This is achieved by placing heavily loaded processors near each other and lightly loaded ones far away from one another in the physical grid locations. The results are mathematically proved for the Algorithms are described.

Keywords—Ascending Sort Index Vector, Effective Communication Load, Effective Distance Matrix, Optimal Placement, Sorting Order.

I. INTRODUCTION

OPTIMUM placement of VLSI blocks has been extensively studied and various solutions are provided [1], [2] for different requirements. In this paper we consider the efficiency of communication as the main criterion while placing the VLSI blocks (say Processors).

When several processors are to be placed in a grid layout, their location can be chosen to minimize the overall effective Communication Load among them. This maximizes the total traffic transportation in a given time.

II. SINGLE LINE PLACEMENT

The Processors are to be uniformly located on a single line grid as shown in fig.1 at L₁, L₂, L₃, ...L_N. The physical distance between adjacent grids is taken as 1 unit.

Fig. 1 Location of Processors

Thus, the different distances are,

$D_{12} = 1$, $D_{13} = 2$, $D_{1N} = N-1$ and so on. The distance between the j th and k th location is given by,

$$D_{jk} = |k - j| \quad (1)$$

with $D_{kk} = 0$

Let P_1, P_2, \dots, P_N be the given processors. The communication among the processors is assumed to be of **Broad-Cast** type and the traffic from one processor to other processors is assumed to be known as follows:

T_{jk} = is the broad cast traffic load to be transported from j to k . T_{jj} is obviously zero. The unit of traffic load can be bytes or packets or frames. The traffic load represents the amount of data to be transported say from the output buffer of a processor.

Important assumption: We assume that the traffic load from a specific source processor to all other processors is of the same magnitude. This value is denoted by T_j for Processor P_j for $j = 1$ to N and is written as,

$$T_1 = T_{12} = T_{13} = \dots = T_{1N}$$

$$T_2 = T_{21} = T_{23} = \dots = T_{2N}$$

.....

$$T_j = T_{j1} = T_{j2} = \dots = T_{jN} \quad (\text{with } T_{jj} = 0) \quad (2)$$

But, T_1, T_2, T_3 etc are generally different from one another. Here, T_j is the traffic load of Processor P_j .

III. EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION LOAD

We define the Effective Communication Load of each processor as follows.

For Processor P_1 ,

$$E_1 = T_{12} \cdot D_{12} + T_{13} \cdot D_{13} + \dots + T_{1N} \cdot D_{1N}$$

For Processor P_2 ,

$$E_2 = T_{21} \cdot D_{21} + T_{23} \cdot D_{23} + \dots + T_{2N} \cdot D_{2N}$$

For Processor P_k ,

$$E_k = T_{k1} \cdot D_{k1} + T_{k2} \cdot D_{k2} + \dots + T_{kN} \cdot D_{kN} \quad \text{that is}$$

$$E_k = \sum_{j=1}^N T_{kj} \cdot D_{kj} \quad (3)$$

Here, each product term represents the traffic load from the source to the destination multiplied by the corresponding distance. This is a metric that represents the transportation burden of that path. The sum of the products gives the total effective load for that Processor.

Thus E_k gives the Effective Communication Load for Processor P_k . The Effective Communication Load (ECL) also represents the energy consumed in transporting the traffic loads through corresponding distances, because, the power required is proportional to the traffic load and the time required is proportional to the distance of travel. Thus the 'traffic-load distance' product represents Energy.

IV. OBJECTIVE OF THE PAPER

The sum of ECL's of each processor is given by Eq.(3) and the overall total is given by,

$$E = E_1 + E_2 + \dots + E_N = \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^N E_{jk} \quad (4)$$

Our objective is to find the optimum placement of given Processors at proper locations to minimize E (the total Effective communication Load for the entire system) as given by Eq.(4).

V. BASIC PRINCIPLE

The basic principle is to place the heavily loaded Processors nearer to each other and lightly loaded ones far away from one another. In other words, higher the traffic load value, lower should be the distance covered by that load and vice-versa. Now the Effective Communication Load of Processor P_i, using Eqs.(3) and (2) is,

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &= T_{12} \cdot D_{12} + T_{13} \cdot D_{13} + \dots + T_{1N} \cdot D_{1N} \\ &= T_1 \cdot D_{12} + T_1 \cdot D_{13} + \dots + T_1 \cdot D_{1N} \\ &= T_1 \cdot (D_{12} + D_{13} + \dots + D_{1N}) \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, for P_j,

$$E_j = T_j \cdot (D_{j1} + D_{j2} + \dots + D_{jN})$$

This is rewritten as,

$$E_j = T_j \cdot D_j \quad (5)$$

where

$$D_j = D_{j1} + D_{j2} + \dots + D_{jN} \quad (6)$$

Now the overall total Effective Communication Load can be expressed using Eqs. (4) and (5) as,

$$E = T_1 \cdot D_1 + T_2 \cdot D_2 + \dots + T_j \cdot D_j + \dots + T_N \cdot D_N$$

That is,

$$E = \sum_{j=1}^N T_j \cdot D_j \quad (7)$$

Thus E is the scalar product of two vectors T and D given by,

$$T = [T_1 \quad T_2 \quad \dots \quad T_N] \quad (8)$$

$$D = [D_1 \quad D_2 \quad \dots \quad D_N] \quad (9)$$

Please note that T_j gives the traffic load of Processor P_j and D_j gives the distance to be covered from location L_j.

Our objective is to minimize E by properly placing the Processors such that when T_k is maximum, D_k is minimum and vice versa. If T is in the descending order, D has to be in the ascending order. *This means, the sort order of T should be opposite to that of D.*

VI. VALUES OF VECTOR D

Consider the case when N=4 as shown in Fig. 2.

Here D₁₂ = 1, D₁₃ = 2 and D₁₄ = 3. Therefore,

$$D_1 = 1 + 2 + 3 = 6$$

Similarly,

$$D_2 = D_{21} + D_{23} + D_{24} = 1 + 1 + 2 = 4$$

$$D_3 = D_{31} + D_{32} + D_{34} = 2 + 1 + 1 = 4$$

$$D_4 = D_{41} + D_{42} + D_{43} = 3 + 2 + 1 = 6$$

Therefore when N=4,

$$D = [6 \quad 4 \quad 4 \quad 6] \quad (10)$$

Similarly when N=5,

$$D = [10 \quad 7 \quad 6 \quad 7 \quad 10] \quad (11)$$

In general, for a given N, the kth element of D, designated as D_k is given by,

$$D_k = \frac{1}{2} [(N-k)(N-k+1) + k(k-1)] \quad (12)$$

For k = 1, 2, ..., N.

Fig. 2 Distances among Processors

The minimum of D occurs at position (N+1)/2 in vector D, when N is odd. When N is even there are 2 equal minimums at positions N/2 and (N/2)+1.

VII. ASCENDING SORT INDEX OF VECTOR D

The Ascending Sort Index Vector (ASIV) of a given vector gives the positions of the smallest element, then the next smallest element and so on in the ascending order. A given vector and its ASIV have the same size. Let

$$G = [G(1) \quad G(2) \quad \dots \quad G(N)]$$

be the ASIV of D, then the elements of G are determined as follows.

G(1) = Position of the smallest element of D in D.

G(2) = Position of the second smallest element of D in D.

.....
 G(k) = Position of the kth smallest element of D in D.

.....
 G(N) = Position of the largest element of D in D.

When two elements of D are equal say at positions i and j with j>i and if D_i is the kth smallest element of D, then D_j is taken as the next smallest element of D for the purpose of ordering.

Therefore G(k) = D_i and G(k+1) = D_j.

Since position j in vector D represents the jth Location,

L_{G(k)} is the Location having the kth smallest distance to other locations. That is,

L_{G(1)} = Location having the smallest distance to others.

L_{G(2)} = Location having the next smallest distance to others.

.....
 L_{G(N)} = Location having the largest distance to others.

G is basically a Permutation Vector. When D is permuted according to G, D gets sorted in the ascending order. The permutation operation is carried as follows.

For $j = 1, 2, \dots, N$ Let

$$F(j) = D(G(j)) \quad (13)$$

Then, from the definition of G, we know that

- $F(1) =$ smallest element of D.
- $F(2) =$ next smallest element of D.
-
- $F(N) =$ largest element of D.

Therefore F is the ascending sorted version of D. Thus ASIV of a given vector represents the ascending sort order of that vector. From Eq.(10), the ASIV of D for $N=4$, written as, ASVI(D) is given by,

$G = \text{ASIV}(D) = \text{ASIV}([6 \ 4 \ 4 \ 6]) = [2 \ 3 \ 1 \ 4]$
 For $N=5$,
 $G = \text{ASIV}(D) = \text{ASIV}([10 \ 7 \ 6 \ 7 \ 10])$
 $= [3 \ 2 \ 4 \ 1 \ 5] \quad (14)$

Because of the symmetric nature of vector D, (see Eqs (10) and (11)) the elements of G which is the AVIS of D can be determined and it can be shown that $G[k] = k$ th element of G is given by,

$G[k] = (N+k)/2$ when N and k are both odd or both even, and
 $G[k] = (N+1-k)/2$ when N odd and k even or vice-versa.

VIII. DESCENDING SORT INDEX OF VECTOR T

The Descending Sort Index Vector (DSIV) of a given vector gives the positions of the largest element, then the next largest element and so on in that order. A given vector and its DSIV have the same size. Let

- $S = [S(1) \ S(2) \ \dots \ S(N)]$
 be the DSIV of the given vector T. Then,
 $S(1) =$ Position of the largest element of T in T.
 $S(2) =$ Position of the second largest element of T in T.

 $S(k) =$ Position of the k th largest element of T in T.

 $S(N) =$ Position of the smallest element of T in T.

Since position j in vector T represents the j th processor, $P_{S(k)}$ is the processor having the k th largest traffic load. That is,

- $P_{S(1)} =$ Processor having the largest traffic load.
- $P_{S(2)} =$ Processor having the second largest traffic loads.
-
- $P_{S(N)} =$ Processor having the smallest traffic load.

Example 1:

Let $N=5$ and
 $T = [50 \ 60 \ 70 \ 80 \ 90]$
 Elements of T give the traffic loads of Processors P_1, P_2, \dots, P_N in that order. Now by inspection,
 $S = \text{DSIV}(T) = [5 \ 4 \ 3 \ 2 \ 1]$
 This means P_5 has the largest traffic load, P_4 has the next highest traffic and so on. The ASIV of D when $N = 5$ as given by Eq.(14) is reproduced here,
 $G = \text{ASIV}(D) = [3 \ 2 \ 4 \ 1 \ 5]$

From the basic principal of minimization of dot product, we know that $\text{DSIV}(T)$ should match with $\text{ASIV}(D)$. Writing one vector below the other we get,

$S = \text{DSIV}(T) = [5 \ 4 \ 3 \ 2 \ 1] =$ order of Processors.
 $G = \text{ASIV}(D) = [3 \ 2 \ 4 \ 1 \ 5] =$ order of Locations.

- From this, we see that
 P_5 should be placed at location 3.
 P_4 should be placed at location 2.

 P_1 should be placed at location 5.

Therefore the general rule is,
 place Processor $P_{S(k)}$ at Location $L_{G(k)}$ for $k=1, 2, \dots, N$

IX. OPTIMUM PLACEMENT ALGORITHM

To place N processors for minimum ECL:

1. Get the T vector from the given traffic load data.
2. Calculate the D vector from Eq.(12).
3. Find the DSIV of T by a suitable sorting algorithm (say Bubble sort) and call it S. That is, get $S = \text{DSIV}(T)$.
4. Similarly, get $G = \text{ASIV}(D)$
5. place Processor $P_{S(k)}$ at Location $L_{G(k)}$ for $k=1, 2, \dots, N$

X. OPTIMUM PLACEMENT ON A 2-DIMENSIONAL GRID

Consider a 2-D grid of M rows and N columns as shown in Fig. 3. The Locations of the grid points are marked as 11, 12,.... and so on. The total manhattan distance to be covered by a given node to reach all other nodes depends on the position of the node. Let the node under consideration be at location (r,c) where r = row value and c = column value of the node position. Then the total distance from this node to all other nodes is given by,

$$D(r, c) = \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^N (|c-j| + |r-i|) \quad (15)$$

for $r = 1, 2, \dots, M$ and $c = 1, 2, \dots, N$

After the summation, this equation can be expressed as

$$D(r, c) = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ M \cdot [c(c-1) + (N-c)(N-c+1)] \right\} + \frac{1}{2} \left\{ N \cdot [r(r-1) + (M-r)(M-r+1)] \right\} \quad (16)$$

For optimum placement, we need to know the position of smallest $D(r,c)$, next smallest $D(r,c)$ and so on. To determine this, we mark the smallest value by metric 1, next smallest by 2 and so on. Consider the Example of a 3x7 grid. The smallest distance occurs at the center of the

Fig. 3 Location of Processors in a 2-D grid

grid and the next smallest at the immediate neighborhood and so on as shown in Fig. 4. We call these distances as effective distances.

5	4	3	2	3	4	5
4	3	2	1	2	3	4
5	4	3	2	3	4	5

Fig. 4 Distribution of Distances when rows =odd and columns=odd

Thus the table of Fig. 4 gives the effective distance matrix ED. For this ED, the ASIV is given by, $G=ASVI(ED)=[(2,4) (2,3) (1,4) (2,5) (3,4) \dots (3,7)]$. The size of G is 15 (which is equal to $M \times N$). $G[1]$ gives the position of the smallest element of D. $G[2]$ gives the position of the next smallest element of D. $G[15]$ gives the position of the largest element of D.

The nature of ED matrix

When the no of rows of the grid M is odd and the no of columns N is odd, the center of the grid area is at row $(M+1)/2$ and column $(N+1)/2$ as in Fig 4. In this case the ij th element of ED is given by,

$$ED(i, j) = 1 + \left| i - \frac{1}{2}(M+1) \right| + \left| j - \frac{1}{2}(N+1) \right| \quad (17)$$

When M and N are both even, the center of the grid is represented by 4 grids as shown in Fig. 5.

4	3	2	2	3	4
3	2	1	1	2	3
3	2	1	1	2	3
4	3	2	2	3	4

Fig. 5 Distribution of Distances when rows =even and columns=even

In this case, the ij th element of ED matrix is given by,

$$ED(i, j) = \left| i - \frac{1}{2}(M+1) \right| + \left| j - \frac{1}{2}(N+1) \right| \quad (18)$$

When M = odd and N = even, the ED matrix appears as shown in Fig. 6.

4	3	2	2	3	4
3	2	1	1	2	3
4	3	2	2	3	4

Fig. 6 Distribution of Distances when Rows =odd and columns=even

In this case, the ij th element of ED matrix is given by,

$$ED(i, j) = \left| i - \frac{1}{2}(M+1) \right| + \left| j - \frac{1}{2}(N+1) \right| + \frac{1}{2} \quad (19)$$

When M = even and N = odd, the ED matrix appears as shown in Fig. 7.

5	4	3	2	3	4	5
4	3	2	1	2	3	4
4	3	2	1	2	3	4
5	4	3	2	3	4	5

Fig. 7 Distribution of Distances when rows =even and columns=odd

In this case, the ij th element of ED matrix is given by Eq.(19).

XI. OPTIMUM PLACEMENT ALGORITHM

To place MxN processors for minimum ECL in a 2-D grid

1. Get the T vector from the given traffic load data. Size of T vector is $M \times N$.
 2. Calculate the ED (Effective Distance) matrix from Eqs.(17), (18) or (19) which is applicable.
 3. Find the DSIV of T by a suitable sorting algorithm (say Bubble sort) and call it S. That is, get $S=DSIV(T)$. Then, $P_{S(k)}$ is the processor having the k th largest traffic load.
 4. Get $G=ASIV(ED)$.
 $G[1]$ = gives the row-column position of the smallest element of ED.
 $G[2]$ = gives the row-column position of the 2 nd smallest element of ED.

 $G[M \times N]$ = gives the row-column position of the largest element of ED.
- In general,
 $G[k]$ = gives the row-column position of the k th smallest

element of ED, for $k=1,2,\dots, M \times N$.

5. Place Processor $P_{S(k)}$ at location given by $G(k)$ for $k=1,2,\dots, M \times N$.

This minimizes the total ECL.

XII. EXAMPLE

Let the grid size be 3×7 . The ED matrix is given as shown in Fig. 4. Let the Traffic Load be given by (values assumed arbitrarily) the T vector of size 21 as,

$$T = [20 \ 25 \ 2 \ 10 \ 15 \ 5 \ 7 \ 9 \ 12 \ 13 \ 24 \ 3 \ 8 \ 21 \\ 11 \ 14 \ 6 \ 23 \ 16 \ 1 \ 19]$$

Then DSIV of T is,

$$S = [2 \ 11 \ 18 \ 14 \ 1 \ 21 \ 19 \ 5 \ 16 \ 10 \ 9 \ 15 \ 4 \ 8 \\ 13 \ 7 \ 17 \ 6 \ 12 \ 3 \ 20]$$

From the matrix of Fig. 4, G is given by

$$G = [(2,4) \ (1,4) \ (2,3) \ (2,5) \ (3,4) \ (1,3) \ (1,5) \\ (2,2) \ (2,6) \ (3,3) \ (3,5) \ (1,2) \ (1,6) \ (2,1) \\ (2,7) \ (3,2) \ (3,6) \ (1,1) \ (1,7) \ (3,1) \ (3,7)]$$

Now, from vectors S and G,

For $k=1$, Processor 2 is placed at location (2,4).

For $k=2$, Processor 11 is placed at location (1,4).

For $k=3$, Processor 18 is placed at location (2,3).

.....
 In general, Processor $P_{S(k)}$ is placed at location $G(k)$.

For $k=21$, Processor 20 is placed at location (3,7).

XIII. PRIORITY CONSIDERATIONS

When different Processors have different Priority levels based on the functionality and system logic, the placement location of the Processors can be modified to take care of the Priorities. Let the Priority of Processor P_k be quantified by a number R_k for $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, M \times N$, such that higher the numerical value of R_k greater is the priority represented by it. For higher overall efficiency, higher priority processors should be placed closer to one another. Therefore from the consideration of priority, a high priority processor should be placed to have a low Effective Distance. The Traffic Load consideration also demands a similar requirement. Hence, the Priority number R_k and Traffic load T_k of Processor P_k are multiplied to get the **Effective Traffic Load** of that Processor, denoted by ET_k and given by,

$$ET_k = R_k \cdot T_k \quad (20)$$

for $k=1,2,\dots,M \times N$.

Thus ET_k of Processor k represents both its Priority and Traffic Load combined together. The ET vector for the system is given by,

$$ET = [R_1 \cdot T_1 \quad R_2 \cdot T_2 \quad \dots \quad R_J \cdot T_J] \quad (21)$$

Where $J=M \times N$ is the total number of Processors.

Now we use the ET vector instead of T vector in the Optimum placement Algorithm of section 11. This takes care of both Traffic Load and Priority requirements.

XIV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented a new technique to determine the placement of Processing Blocks to achieve maximum communication efficiency in both single line and 2-D grids.

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Aswatha A.R received B.E Degree from Mysore University in 1991, M.Tech Degree from M.I.T Manipal in 1996, M.S. Degree from B.I.T.S. Pilani in 2002, pursuing Ph.D degree in Dr. M.G.R University. Currently he is working as Associate Professor in Electronics & Communication Department, Dayanand Sagar College of Engineering, Bangalore, India. His main research Interests include Analysis and design of Low Power VLSI Circuits and Image Processing.

T. Basavaraju received B.E Degree from U.V.C.E, Bangalore in 1962, M.Sc (Engineering) Degree from PSGCT, Coimbatore in 1967, Ph.D degree from Bangalore University, Bangalore, India, in 1980. Currently he is working as Director (Accademics) in Sri Revana Siddeshwara Institute of Technology, Bangalore India. His main research Interests include Analysis and design of Device Technology.

Bhaskara Rao N. received B.E Degree in Electrical Engineering from UVCE Bangalore, M.E Degree in Control Systems from IISC Bangalore, India. Currently he is working as Professor in Computer Science Engineering, Department, Dayanand Sagar College of Engineering, Bangalore, India. His main research Interests include VLSI Design and Image Processing.